

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FINANCIAL RESOURCES
MOBILISATION AND INTERNAL EFFICIENCY OF PUBLIC
TECHNICAL TRAINING INSTITUTIONS
IN BUNGOMA COUNTY, KENYA**

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Abstract:

This paper looks at the relationship that exists between financial resource mobilisation and internal efficiency of public technical training institutions located in the county of Bungoma Kenya. For the objectives of technical training to be attained, financial resources is needed. This is because, instructional resources, infrastructural facilities or human resources all depend on the budget that their institutions develops and utilises on yearly basis. The study was conducted in four public technical training institutions in Bungoma County. The methodology for the study was mixed employing qualitative and quantitative methods. Data was collected through questionnaires and interviews from the following respondents; 4 principals, 16 managers in charge of IGAs, and 239 tutors from the four institutions mentioned above. The sample size involved 4 TTIs principles, 16 resource mobilisation managers and 150 tutors. The respondents were selected using stratified and systematic random sampling methods and purposive (judgmental) sampling methods. Data was collected through questionnaire and interview schedules. Analysis of data was performed using descriptive and inferential statistics to answer research question and test the research hypothesis. Computed correlation values ($r=0.336$ and $p=0.001$) showed that there existed weak positive relationship between financial resources mobilisation and internal efficiency of public training institutions in Bungoma County. Therefore, public TTIs need to increase their financial resource mobilisation strategies with the hope of increasing internal efficiency. Moreover, automation of financial system in public technical training institutions in the study is necessary.

Keywords: relationship, financial, resources, mobilisation, internal & efficiency

1. Introduction

Technical and Vocational Education is an indispensable element for socio-economic, political and technological development of a nation (Psacharopoulos & Patrinos, 2004; Simiyu, 2009; Odundo & Rambo, 2013). World Bank (2010) report showed that almost all higher education systems in Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries are increasingly under pressure due to rising student populations and mounting costs of teaching and research activities. TVET institutions have recorded changes in the last five years due to; enrollment growth, declining state funding for tertiary education, devolution or decentralization of responsibility to the institutional level, governmental regulations to improve quality in teaching and learning, globalization and internationalization of higher education, international competition for funds, faculty, and students and new technologies such as ICT among others (World Bank, 2010). This implies that the rapid growth in the number of students is a challenge to the sustainable financing of tertiary education. Provision of quality basic education has been a priority of the Kenya government since independence, as stipulated in relevant policy documents, including Kenya vision 2030 and the basic education act 2013, the Kenya constitution 2010 (Waweru & Muturi, 2015). These efforts to devote meaningful funding to education is justified against backdrop that available evidence from literature review suggests a positive and significant correlation between indicators of quality and financial allocation (Oketch & Ngware, 2012). The World Bank (1990) emphasized sourcing of additional; sources of financial support or reducing the unit cost through greater efficiency as the solution on public finance at a time when government funds are stagnant or even declining in many developing countries. Principals of TVET institutions are thus tasked with responsibility to initiating appropriate financial mobilisation strategies such as income generating activities, aimed at enhancing resource mobilization in order to run their schools effectively and efficiently. This study checks on the financial resource mobilisation strategies that public technical training institutions in Bungoma County are using to ensure internal efficiency.

2. Problem Statement

The issue of finance is at the heartbeat of every organisation for organisation organs to operate smoothly. Schools needs finances (from government, students fees, non – governmental organisations, income generating projects) to run school programmes. Hence, without finance, all programmes in the institutions come to a halt. Data from Kenya Economy Survey (2016) showed that despite increase in the number of technical training institutions around the country recording higher enrolment, completion rate of students enrolled in such institutions remained low. For instance, In Bungoma, a research by Kitui (2015) established that youth polytechnics had inadequate physical facilities and finally lacked enough trained and qualified teachers. This showed that

provision of TVET education faces critical challenges relating to adequate human resource and physical facilities. The research by Kitui (2015) was on vocational training institutions while this study focused on the initiatives taken by public technical training institutions in Bungoma County to mobilise financial resources to help meet and realise higher internal efficiency in their institutions.

2.1 Purpose of the Study

The objective of this study was to determine the relationship that existed between financial resource mobilisation and internal efficiency of public TTIs in Bungoma County, Kenya.

2.2 Research Hypothesis

The paper tests the following research hypotheses.

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between financial resource mobilisation and internal efficiency of technical training institutions in Bungoma County.

3. Literature Review

Successful financial resource mobilization has evolved into a key function for many present-day international public administrations (IPAs). A large number of organizations (including educational institutions) currently depend to significant shares on often earmarked voluntary contributions, requiring substantial efforts to maintain or even increase resource levels (Patz & Goetz, 2017) to ensure their goals are attained. However, little is still known about what role the degree to which technical training institutions mobilise resources to ensure internal efficiency, this is focus of this study. For effective implementation of TVET curriculum, supporting resources need to be adequate (Esongo, 2017). TVET institutions may need additional financial support to run activities that are vital to attainment of internal efficiency goals and students' academic achievement. Financial resources are a key factor for successful implementation and they come from the allocated funds of the government, registration and tuition fees as the case may be. In addition, incentives in the form of remunerative power (such as salaries, commissions, fringe benefits) is usually the most effective means of inducing in policy implementers the willingness to achieve a satisfactory standard of enforcement and compliance (Goetz & Patz, 2016).

Sufficient incentives, both monetary and non-monetary provided to policy implementers will likely make them more willing to comply with government policy (Bayram & Graham 2016). The former includes salaries and other fringe benefits while the latter includes career path development such as promotion and recognition. Career path development such as promotion and relocation, as well as other benefits, plays a key role in strengthening professional growth and skills, and has an impact on internal efficiency (Esongo, 2017). Wayua (2015) observed that Kenyan government being committed to providing adequate teaching and learning resources by financing education for all its citizens. In spite of this commitment, sufficiency of resources

remains unachieved in public schools due to inadequate financial resources in most parts of the country necessitating for the need for resource mobilisation in Kenyan educational institutions like public TTIs.

UNICEF (2012) in its report on public finance in East Asia identified a number of bottlenecks in mobilization and allocation of resources that included a lack of clear standards for schools and classrooms, insufficient understanding and monitoring of the relationship between quality inputs and outcomes. This report recommended schools that do not meet standards should receive more funding in order to address factors contributing to the disparity. This report further suggested the need for schools to identify key performance indicators so that schools can link budget allocations and outcomes and to strengthen and human capacity to better measure inputs and outputs. It is important that the challenges faced by principals are identified; those that have been resolved and those that remain unresolved so that action measures may be taken to overcome them and improve on resource mobilization and prioritize resource allocation in order to improve on performance. A similar study was needed to be carried out in Bungoma County in order to provide solutions of challenges related to mobilization of resources that have remained unresolved.

In Israel, Yemini, Addi-Racah and Katarivas (2014) examined school principals from the perspective of their schools' entrepreneurship. This study examined 10 school principals of different educational streams in Israel, who have been identified as entrepreneurs by their peers and supervision authorities. Principals' entrepreneurship was found to be driven by particular values and visions that are important to them, which are then adopted by the school staff. They engaged the school staff and win over their support for the suggested venture. Hence, their ability to execute their vision and introduce innovations depends on creating commitment of the school staff to their vision. Nwaokeonu (2014) studied the perceived impact of some factors on the resources allocation processes of the Nigerian universities. The study adopted the interpretive qualitative approach aimed at an in-depth understanding of the resource allocation experiences of key university personnel and their perceived impact of the contextual factors affecting such processes. The resources allocation process issues in the Nigerian universities may be categorised into people (core and peripheral units' challenge, and politics and power); process (resources allocation processes); and resources (critical financial shortage and resources dependence response). Akinsolu (2012) investigated the relationship between resource utilization and internal efficiency indicators in Nigeria public secondary schools with a view to appraise whether the public secondary schools in the country make the best use of resources allotted in turning out graduates with minimal wastage. A correlational study; stratified random sampling technique (SRST), based on the six geo-political zones was used to select 250 Local Government Areas (LGAs) out of the existing 774 LGAs representing 32%. The correlation matrix table showed that all variables of Resource Utilization had positive relationship with internal efficiency. This attested to the fact that resources are vital for educational system production function. The research by Akinsolu was conducted in Nigeria while this was conducted in technical training institutions in Bungoma County.

Esongo (2017) examined of the extent to which the availability of resources related to the efficiency of the school system within the framework of the implementation of competency-based teaching approaches in Cameroon. The study employed a mix of probability sampling approaches, namely simple, cluster and stratified random sampling techniques to select the 375 teacher-respondents and purposive sampling technique to select the 26 principals for the study. The findings indicated that there is a significant relationship between the availability of resources and the efficiency of the school system. The magnitude of the relationship that exists was rated low. The research by Esongo was conducted in secondary schools while this research was conducted in Kenyan technical and vocational institutions. Research done in Tanzania by Galabawa (2008) on ways of enhancing education quality and efficiency cite that policies instituted in the country in the 1990s through 2000 which included vision 2025, civil and institutional financial reforms, education development programmes, poverty rehabilitation, debt relief initiatives, all these were applied as a tool for economic and qualitative change especially in education. He showed that fundraising acts are stable sources of revenue for schools. Other sources identified in the study included parental contributions during registrations, admission of new pupils, raffles and mixed music-evenings. Galabawa (2008) identified seven sources of finance in the Lake Victoria zone that included parental contribution, school economic projects, school fees, funds from local community development associations and school funding bodies. This study sought to find out if similar methods are used to mobilize resources by technical training institutions in Bungoma County, Kenya.

In Kenya, Wayua (2015) study was to find out methods of resource mobilization and allocation amongst subjects in public secondary schools in Makueni County. This study utilized the cost-effective model that emphasized on educational evaluation and how this can be used to evaluate instructional programs. The target population included 129 principals, 877 teachers and, 7,273 students. The total target population was 8,279. Sampling was done using random and non-random methods. The sample was drawn from 129 secondary schools. The findings of the study revealed that teaching and learning resources were majorly acquired through purchase by school by using government funds (69.23%) and donations by NGOs (61.14%). Teaching and learning resources were majorly allocated according to class size or enrollment per subject (80.77%) and resources available in schools (69.23%). The major challenges in mobilizing and allocating school resources were lack of enough funds (82.61%) and large class enrollment (69.23%). Parents' involvement and prioritizing critical areas of teaching and learning were suggested as the major possible ways of curbing the challenges. The research by Wayua was in secondary schools while this research was conducted in public technical training institutions.

4. Materials and Methods

The methodology for the study was mixed employing qualitative and quantitative methods. Data was collected through questionnaires and interviews from the following

respondents; 4 principals, 16 managers in charge of IGAs, and 239 tutors from the four institutions mentioned above. The sample size involved 4 TTIs principles, 16 resource mobilisation managers and 150 tutors. The respondents were selected using stratified and systematic random sampling methods and purposive (judgmental) sampling methods. Data was collected through questionnaire and interview schedules. Analysis of data was performed using descriptive and inferential statistics to answer research question and test the research hypothesis. SPSS facilitated coding, entry and analysis of quantitative data. Descriptive statistics; frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviations were used. Karl Pearson correlation statistics was computed to test the relationship between financial resource mobilisation and internal efficiency of public technical training institutions in Bungoma County, Kenya.

5. Results and Discussions

To answer the main research question for this study, tutors were asked to state the frequency to which financial resource mobilisation activities was conducted in their institution using the following scale: 1), rarely (2), sometimes (3), often (4) and always (5). The responses are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Financial Resource Mobilisation Strategies in Public TTIs

Resources	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always	Mean	SD
There is a proper criteria for financial resource distribution in our TTI to improve financial management	13 (10.0%)	55 (42.3%)	29 (22.3%)	29 (22.3%)	4 (3.1%)	2.6615	1.03095
Expenditure is properly accounted for and is done according to priorities set to reduce wastage	17 (13.1%)	56 (43.1%)	32 (24.6%)	22 (16.9%)	3 (2.3%)	2.5231	.99779
Our institution holds various fundraising functions to promote institution wide development	24 (18.5%)	55 (42.3%)	33 (25.4%)	16 (12.3%)	2 (1.5%)	2.3615	.97252
Our institutional management has the capacity to mobilise resources to attract more students	4 (3.1%)	28 (21.5%)	30 (23.1%)	56 (43.1%)	12 (9.2%)	3.3385	1.01580
All stakeholders are involved in resource mobilisation activities to ensure objectives are realised	16 (12.3%)	43 (33.1%)	38 (29.2%)	27 (20.8%)	6 (4.6%)	2.7231	1.07123
Resource mobilisation is an ongoing exercise in our institution as it increases internal efficiency	7 (5.4%)	29 (22.3%)	28 (21.5%)	59 (45.4%)	7 (5.4%)	3.2308	1.03083
Composite scores						2.8064	1.01985

Asked on whether there was proper criteria for financial resource distribution in their TTI to improve on prudential financial management, Table 1 result indicated that 13 (10.0%) said there was no such criteria, 55 (42.3%) said that it was rarely done, 29 (22.3%) said that it was sometimes done, 29 (22.3%) was often done and 4 (3.1%) said that it was always done. The computed statistics shows that sometimes ($M=2.66$ and $SD=1.03$) developed criteria for financial resource distributions in their institutions which is a critical factor towards attaining prudential financial management standards. The results implies that due to poor budgeting planning and implementation process, financial resource distribution is not properly conducted which may affect the performance of various activities within the school. In tandem with the study findings, Nwaokeonu (2014) research in Nigeria found out that the allocation of allocation of resources in the six universities did not follow a standard scientific assessment process. This suggested that the universities pursued resource allocation in no systematic order. This appeared to have resulted in lack of transparency and loss of faith on the part of the resource managers.

Secondly, 56 (43.1%) of respondents said that expenditure is rarely accounted for and it is rarely done with respect to priorities set with the aim of reducing wastage, 32 (24.6%) were of the opinion that this was sometimes done, 22 (16.9%) said this was often done and only 3 (2.3%) said it was always done according to the requirements. The results show that expenditure is not always ($M=2.52$ and $SD=0.99$) done according to the laid procedures hence resulting to wastage and financial impropriety incidents. This implies that there due to accountability issues, most institutions cannot account for what they have spent because what was done using the money given was not according to priorities set thereby bringing the issue of financial mismanagement in schools that puts the internal efficiency at lower level. To correct the above issue, Awuor (2015) argued that to avoid mismanagement and misappropriation of school funds there is need to keep up to date financial books of accounts.

Results further showed that 55 (42.3%) of tutors indicated that their institution rarely hold various fundraising functions to promote institution wide development, 24 (18.5%) said that they did not regularly hold fundraising events, 33 (22.4%) sometimes held fundraising, 16 (12.3%) often held fundraising and 2 (1.5%) always held fundraising events. The responses shows that most institutions rarely ($M=2.36$ and $SD=0.97$) conduct fund raising events with the aim of purchasing and constructing new facilities in schools. This shows that most institutional management have not yet identified the significant role that harambees plays towards improving educational resources in TVET institutions. The study contradicts with Awuor et al. (2016) who established that a boost in harambee collections strategy would result into minimal increase in student performance. This state of affairs is further reinforced by findings that showed that the institutional management did not have full capacity to mobilise more resources with the aim of increasing enrolment ($M=3.33$ and $SD=1.01$). Only 56 (43.1%) of respondents indicated to have full capacity of mobilising resources with the aim of expanding their school student intakes. This implies that the low level of fundraising activities is due to inability by institutional board of management to

understand how to mobilise resources for increasing internal efficiency of those institutions. Another aspect that could explain the inability of institutional management to mobilise financial resources could be due to their failure to involve other stakeholders in planning, decision-making and implementation of programmes.

In line with study findings, Kibet et al. (2013) found out that most of the institutions did not have officers or officers or committees in charge of resource mobilization. In addition, in most of the institutions, the staffs were not adequately involved in resource mobilization efforts. However in contrast to these findings, Yemini et al. (2014) research in Israel found out that principals are not hindered by funding constraints in implementing visions they have dedicated themselves to. They did not hesitate to begin a new project, even when funding for it had not been secured. They appeared confident in their ability to fundraise as needed. As such, they appeared ready to take risks. This argument is supported by the findings that showed that only 6 (4.6%) admitted that stakeholders were involved in resource mobilisation activities hence affecting schools goals and objectives. The mean statistics showed that stakeholders were sometimes ($M=2.72$ and $SD=1.07$) involved in resource mobilisation activities. This implies that majority of stakeholders feel ignored as their input is not valued in making efforts of ensuring that schools attain higher internal efficiency levels. The study findings is supported by Awuor et al. (2016) who found out that high returns from income generating activities will translate into increased internal efficiency as measured by student performance index. This study finding is different from what Yemini et al. (2014) found in Israel whereby principals as entrepreneurs never worked alone. They engaged the school staff and win over their support for the suggested venture. Hence, their ability to execute their vision and introduce innovations depends on creating commitment of the school staff to their vision.

When asked as to whether resource mobilisation was an ongoing exercise in their institutions with the goal of increasing internal efficiency levels, 7 (5.4%) disagreed, 29 (22.3%) mentioned that it is rarely done, 28 (21.5%) agreed that it is sometimes done, 59 (45.4%) admitted it to be often done and 7 (5.4%) mentioned that it was always done. The result therefore shows that resource mobilisation is an ongoing exercise that is sometimes ($M=3.23$ and $SD=1.03$) conducted in the institutions under study. The result therefore shows that financial resource mobilisation is not a significant process that TTIs in Bungoma County consider and this could have significant effect on achievement of internal efficiency targets. The study finding coincides with Haramoto (2015) who found out that there was no income generating activities in Sudan TTIs. In addition, Kibet et al. (2013) implied that despite their potential, majority of campuses of the private universities were not able to mobilize as many resources as possible. Other potential sources of resources were yet to be fully exploited for resources mobilization. The findings show that generally, the training on resource mobilization is yet to have a significant impact on resource mobilization efforts among private universities in the study area.

Composite scores showed that financial resource mobilisation was averagely (M=2.80 and SD=1.01) conducted in public TTIs centres in Bungoma County. Through interviews, the resource mobilisation managers were asked to indicate the achievements made in mobilising financial resources in improving efficiency of public TTIs. One resource mobilisation officer No. 6 said the following:

“Department involved in budgeting and income generation from electrical hire services”.

Another resource mobilisation officer No. 4 fronted this aspect:

“We have enforced school fees collection and BOM and school administration members have embraced budgeting controls.”

Furthermore, officer number 16 remarked that:

“Opening of new learning programmes and additional courses/more campuses. Established short innovative courses i.e. Garment making and mushroom production. Mobilisation of HELB loans application for needy students to raise fees. Making of effective budgets during the financial year.”

The above responses from resource mobilisation officers show that various strategies are used to mobilise financial resources in schools.

The research hypothesis (H₀₁) stated that: There is no significant relationship between financial resource mobilisation and internal efficiency of technical training institutions in Bungoma County.

To check on the kind of relationship that existed between financial resource mobilisation and internal efficiency in public TTIs, a Karl Pearson correlation was computed. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between Financial Resource Mobilisation and Internal Efficiency of Public TTIs

		Financial resource mobilisation	Internal efficiency
Financial resource mobilisation	Pearson Correlation	1	.336**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	130	130
Internal efficiency	Pearson Correlation	.336**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	130	130

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field data (2018).

Table 2 Correlation statistics shows that there exist a weak positive relationship ($r=0.336$ and $p=0.001$) between financial resource mobilisation activities and internal efficiency of public technical institutions in Bungoma County. The results also appears to be significant at 99% confidence level ($p<0.01$) and leads to rejection of the null hypothesis for the study. This implies that financial resource mobilisation activities were low and which did not affect internal efficiency of public technical institutions. However, the research result imply that increased financial resource mobilisation would increase internal efficiency of public technical training institutions in Bungoma county. The research somewhat coincides with Awuor et al. (2016) established that financial resources mobilised through income generating activities were found to be positively related to internal efficiency of the schools. The proceeds were used to subsidize the lunch and boarding budgets hence releasing more funds for tuition related activities. Therefore, to positively influence school internal efficiency effective resource mobilisation strategies must be employed. Similarly, Kibet et al. (2013) concluded that apart from tuition fees, other potential sources of resources are yet either to be fully exploited or mobilized on a limited scale. It was also noted that despite their potential, majority of centers/campuses of the private universities were not able to mobilize as many resources as possible. Furthermore, Esongo (2017) research in Cameroon found out that there was a significant relationship between the availability of resources and the efficiency of the school system. The magnitude of the relationship that exists was rated low. This implies that when resource mobilization activities are low, internal efficiency of public TTIs is greatly affected. The findings of this study is in sharp contrast to Akinsolu (2012) findings that financial and human resources utilization seem not to have any relationship on student repetition rate, dropout rate, and fail-out rate and graduation rate (aspects of internal efficiency of public TTIs).

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

Principals mentioned that they ensured that financial resource mobilisation was maintained through proper procurement, others mentioned that it was on average while others mentioned that they had set up budgetary controls and set up of institutional financial accounting system. The study revealed that there were not a standard procedure in which the public TTIs carried out their resource allocation processes. Above all, it appears there were no scientific ways of assessing departmental needs for inclusion in the year's budget. In order to supplement the school financial resources, community members could be mobilised to pool up their monetary resources in form of harambees. Responses from tutors showed that financial resource mobilisation was moderately ($M=2.80$ and $SD=1.01$) conducted by school management in public TTIs in Bungoma County. This is supported by 43.1% who said that their management often had the capacity to mobilise financial resources with the aim of improving TTI curriculum implementation. Research mobilisation process was found not to be regular ongoing exercises in those institutions. Stakeholders were also found to be moderately involved in resource mobilisation activities and this justifies the

outcome that financial resource mobilisation activities were not conducted as expected. However, research findings showed that fundraising initiatives were rarely done in the four public TTIs. The study concludes that there exists a statistically significant relationship between financial resource mobilisation and utilisation strategies on internal efficiency of public technical training institutions in Bungoma County, Kenya. This implied that financial resource mobilisation initiatives were not regularly conducted and that it was why it affected internal efficiency to a lower degree. To improve financial resource mobilisation, there is need for those institutions to automate their financial management services. All management staff also needs to be retrained on integrity and accountability courses so that they understand the consequences of providing expenditures that is not supported with proof.

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